

A Web-based HRI Interface for Teleoperation of Overground and Underground Robots

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Abstract—This paper presents an advanced human-robot interaction (HRI) interface that offers intuitive teleoperation of the BADGER’s system surface and subsurface robots. The interface provides the proper tools for a familiar user to analyze the robot’s environment and guide the robots autonomously or with teleoperation in order to firstly perform the scanning of the designated underground area by exploiting the surface robot’s GPR antenna, and secondly for the planning and operation of the subsurface robot during the drilling procedure. Moreover, the interface incorporates 3D simulation technologies that provide accurate representations of the robot’s surroundings using the robot’s sensors, while effective mechanisms have been implemented for the systematic teleoperation of the subsurface robot with an easy to use graphical user interface (GUI). The HRI interface is integrated within the ROS framework and is built as a web application that can be operated through a smartphone or a tablet offering additional mobility to the operator.

Index Terms—HRI interface, robotic teleoperation, underground robot interfaces, robot GUI

I. INTRODUCTION

The first user interfaces for robotic applications began with the need of humans to remotely handle highly radioactive items while preventing any exposure of the operator [1]. Since then many advancements have been made in the field of robotic teleoperation, mainly for humanoid robots in social and hazardous environments. The usage of such systems provides obvious advantages of reduced costs, removing humans from harms way, or enabling entirely new applications that were previously impossible like remotely operating a planetary rover system [2]. Authors in [3] developed a GUI for the remote teleoperation and control of an Explosive Ordnance Disposal robot deployed in parking lot capable of removing vehicles that block suspect vehicle trapped with explosive mechanisms. Other important areas that have benefited from robotic teleoperation is agriculture, where robotic sprayers have been controlled through multiple interaction interfaces [4] and underwater imaging, where a teleoperated robot has been used to digitalize the seafloor [5]. In each aforementioned application, an effective and intuitive human-robot interaction (HRI) interface was developed in order to provide a comprehensive representation of the environment to the operator while offering the essential tools to control the robot. The

majority of the developed HRI systems in the literature are graphical, like the interface used for personal service robots in [6], the measuring of situation awareness interface for search and rescue applications in [8], the web-based interface for elderly users of the robot-era multi-robot services [7], and the mobile-based interface for assessing the importance of operator mobility in [9]. While most HRI interfaces are graphical, there are many developments in voice-based and tactile-based interfaces where the aim is to off-load a part of the feedback to other human senses, specifically to the sense of touch or sound to reduce the load due to the interface, and as a consequence, to increase the level of operator situation awareness [10], [11].

In our work, we have developed an advanced and intuitive HRI system for the simultaneous control of surface and subsurface robots of the BADGER system [12]. BADGER is a complex robotic system that consists of two robotic components. The first one comprises a surface operating robot that tows a trailer with a Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR), responsible to perform coupled surface/subsurface mapping of the area of interest in order to detect underground obstacles. The produced coupled surface/subsurface map are utilized by the underground robot for the planning and navigation procedures required for the autonomous drilling. The interface visualizes the real environment through a 3D representation provided from the robots’ sensors. State of art path planning algorithms offer automatic path generation for both robots that can be visualized by the interfaces to increase operators situation awareness. Furthermore, by exploiting advanced teleoperation mechanisms we have managed to offer through the web-based GUI an effortless way of interaction, addressing situations where the operator needs to control the robots automatically or manually. We have used the latest web technologies in order for the interface to be lightweight and portable, while integration with the Robotic Operating System (ROS) through the `roslibJS` [13] and `rod3dJS` libraries provides the necessary tools for the interconnections and communication between the different modules and the main nodes of the application.

II. OVERVIEW OF THE HRI ARCHITECTURE

The HRI of the BADGER robotic system has been developed to operate on a web browser using widespread libraries and frameworks. This renders the interface widely accessible and portable since it can be accessed from various devices like tablets and laptops without the need for any installation or configuration process. The BADGER HRI is based on a web

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GUI and employs various web technologies such as HTML to define the content of the application, CSS to specify the layout of the application and JavaScript to program the behavior and the interconnections of the application's modules. The web interface is integrated with the Robot Operating System (ROS) environment in order to monitor, configure and control the BADGER robots. This integration is achieved by making use of ROS node *rosbridge_server*, responsible for receiving JSON string messages and sending the commands to the main ROS nodes and vice versa. Furthermore, there is extensive incorporation of two popular open source JavaScript libraries, *roslibJS* and *ros3DJS*, which provide tools for visualizing, publishing, subscribing, service and actionlib calling, URDF parsing, and other essential ROS functionalities. In particular, *ros3DJS* allows the 3D visualization of the robot and the environment using 3D meshes, pointclouds and paths to offer a simulated view of the real procedure to the user. *Roslibjs* uses *WebSockets* to connect with ROS and is used to interconnect the users interface interactions with the system and the robot itself. These interactions include "button" events (clicks) or input of values for the task planning. Using *roslibJS*, the modules can post messages to ROS topics or execute ROS services that provide advanced functionalities to the application.

Fig. 1. Overview of the Graphical User Interface

III. INTERFACE MODULES DESCRIPTION

The user can "navigate" through the interface by exploiting the navigation bar on the left (see Fig. (1)), which encapsulates the main modules of the system that need to be accessed in a sequential order. Using simple buttons, the interface guides the user intuitively through the process of selecting an area on the map, inspecting the underground scans, planning a drilling path for the robot and either selecting autonomous operation or teleoperation of the underground robot. The functionalities that correspond to the buttons of the navigation bar are presented in the following subsections.

A. Area Selection

The area selection module (see Fig. 2) is used to define an area on the map, which will be of interest for the BADGER robot operation. As such, this area is the one where the rover is supposed to scan the underground for any obstacles using the GPR.

For this purpose, we make use of the Google Maps API where the user has to select four points on the map to create a rectangle, defining the area that the rover has to scan. An additional marker represents the rovers position on the map using the surface rover onboard GPS system. If the user is not satisfied with the chosen positions, s/he can clear the markers and redefine the scanning area.

After making sure that the area has been selected, the positions of the borders can be further refined in the virtual environment of ROS using interactive markers that can be translated in the 2D planar surface where the rover operates. To extract the markers positions, the distance in meters (latitudinal and longitudinal) of every marker on the map with respect to the rover is computed, while by using *roslibJS* the positions are published to the interface using specific messages to the respective marker topic. The refining of the marker positions is an easy and user friendly task in the virtual space, visualized using *ros3DJS*, as the user has a clear view of the rovers position with respect to the markers since the ground is organized with meter markings as exhibited in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Area selection in the GUI

B. Scanning operation

The scanning operation module (see Fig. 3) is used to provide the user with visual representations of the scanning area and the detected pipes with geospatial information in the respective subsurface area. By selecting the Start scanning button, a message is sent to the respective topic using *roslibJS* and the rover uses an automatically generated Boustrophedon-like path, constrained by the markers positions of the previous module to begin the scanning of the defined area. The generated path is a global path that the rover has to follow, while performing surface mapping, b-scan collection and autonomous navigation.

Using *ros3DJS*, the rover is visualized in the virtual environment, while its RGBD sensors provide the viewer with a point-cloud representation of the surrounding area. The detected

underground utilities, by exploiting the GPR antenna and the B-Scan processing modules, are represented with red cylinders in real time while the rover is still scanning, so the user can instantly have a clear view of the underground findings as seen in Fig. 3.

On the left panel, the interface provides the user with the GPR antenna scan images as well as the reference images from the stereo camera. Specifically, on the top is the left image from the stereo pair, which is used for the computation of the disparity image through the stereo correspondence algorithm and the features tracking in order to produce the rovers motion estimation. On the bottom is the B-SCAN image formulated by the horizontal polarized channels of the GPR and is built while the rover performs straight routes. More specifically, considering that an A-scan is the signal received by the antenna receiver due to the underground and air/ground reflections of an initial stimulating pulse transmitted by the antenna transmitter, a B-scan is simply a concatenation of stacked A-scans recorder along a scanning direction. A single column of a B-scan corresponds to a specific position on the rovers trajectory, while a single row corresponds to a specific time. The system produces simultaneously 9 B-Scan images which the user has the option to select the desired one, a functionality which becomes available right after the rover has completed a stride or the user has selected a specific image that has been created previously. Thus, by incorporating drop down menus in the GUI, the user can choose a specific B-SCAN s/he can also choose a specific channel of the GPR antenna that needs to be visualized. In the next version of the GUI it has already been foreseen to graphically illustrate in the GUI also the C-Scans in the same manner as the B-Scan. A C-scan is a concatenation of a series of consecutive B-scans. In a C-Scan the height and width of the 2D image corresponds to spatial positions on the 2d scanning grid and the values of the image correspond to the processed, migrated and thresholded values of the received signals at certain time ranges.

In order to prevent unexpected situations (e.g. the rover deviates from its commanded path), the user can abort the scanning operation by exploiting the respective button in the GUI. During the rover motion, the left reference image from the stereo pair is continuously availed and after the completion of the scanning the B-SCAN images are available and can be inspected, the “Next” button is activated and the user can use it to proceed with the drill planning module. Several diagnostic signals for the continuous inspection of the surface operating system are foreseen to provide situation awareness to the user. For example, the system error “Odometry Lost” for the surface rover indicates that the localization of the robot is of poor quality and the user can intervene through the GUI to abort the procedure and repeat it from scratch by selecting again the scanning area. Another signal is referred to the GPR status “GPR connection Lost”, which indicates that the device is operable or the connection with it has lost due to low battery.

Fig. 3. Scanning operation in BADGER’s GUI. The thicker green line shows the progress of the robot navigation indicating the coverage of the area to be scanned.

C. Drill planning

The drill planning module is used to provide the user with a clear representation of the scanned environment that has been generated through the previous modules. This representation will allow the user to define the entry and exit points of the underground BADGER robot before automatically generating the drilling path. Using the same graphical objects that have been described in the previous module, a point-cloud generated by the rovers RGB-D sensor and red cylinders to represent the objects detected by the rovers GPR antenna, the interface helps the user to visualize the drilling environment.

Firstly, the user has to use the provided entry and exit point markers as seen in Fig. 4 to define the entry and exit point of the underground robot, respectively. The markers are generated using ros3DJS and can be moved freely in the 3D space in accordance to the users input. The Human Machine Interface that will allow such interaction with the markers is basically the Mouse of the PC, however in case of utilization of mobile devices interaction with touch screen is also supported. The green marker represents the entry point whereas the red marker represents the exit point for the underground robot. Once the user is satisfied with the selection s/he can use the “Generate path” button, so that the drilling path can then be generated by the system.

As illustrated in Fig. 5, the drilling path is generated instantly and is represented by a red line which, as shown therein, avoids subsurface obstacles. Yellow rectangular boxes are generated around the detected objects to provide a visual representation of the area that has to be avoided. The drilling path is generated automatically using the Dijkstra algorithm that defines the shortest distance between two points. Specifically, it considers the 3D volumetric map of the sub/surface to construct a connected graph and by exploiting graph traversing

Fig. 4. Entry and exit point markers.

solutions the shortest obstacle-free path is calculated and visualized in the UI. The back-end of this module considers the constraints of the underground robot motion capabilities by applying a parameter specific B-Spline interpolation among the Dijkstra graph points and by regulating accordingly the neighborhood sampling during path planning. Furthermore, the user can freely move the entry and exit point markers after the path is generated, and new paths are re-planned until a satisfying path has been inferred by the system. When the preferred path is inspected, the user can select with the “Next” button to proceed with the autonomous drilling module.

Fig. 5. Auto-generated drilling path marked with red.

D. Autonomous drilling

The autonomous drilling application, as shown in Fig. 6, accepts as input the path generated by the drill planning module and executes the autonomous operation of the BADGER underground robot. For this purpose, it sends the path waypoints to the autonomous control module of BADGER robot, which in turn generates a sequence of closed loop control commands so that the robot moves along the desired path.

During the robots operation, a series of charts, on the right side of the panel, provide to the operator with feedback information on thrust force, drill-head torque, temperature, and feed rate during the drill process. The autonomous drilling pane comprises two windows which offer to the operator 3D visual feedback (lateral and top view) of the drilling process in relation to the underground map and utilities. Hence, the operator is able to monitor the deviations of the robot motion from the desired path.

The 3D representation of the underground is achieved using the same graphical objects that have been described in the previous module, i.e. a point-cloud generated by the rovers RGBD sensor and red cylinders to represent the objects detected by the rovers GPR antenna. Note that the modeling of the surface/subsurface is performed in the 3D space. Specifically, the surface rover motion is calculated in 3D coordinates and the registration of the hyperbola apexes (red points in Fig. 6 of the B-Scans undergoes a topographic correction inherited by the registered rovers motion estimation. The operator is able to stop and start the procedure at will by clicking on the MASTER Start/Stop buttons. In case that the autonomous execution raises an alert due to some failure to follow the path, then the operator can use the Manual Drilling pane described in the next section, to either drive the robot to the goal or to drive the robot backwards out of the drilling bore.

Fig. 6. Autonomous drilling module with top and side views.

E. Tele-operated drilling

In this section, we describe the Manual drilling or tele-operation module of the Badger robot. Through this mode, the robot is solely controlled by the human via a Graphical User Interface (GUI), which is actually an additional feature of the Web-GUI. The tele-operation module is based on ROS implementation, using Python programming language, and can be employed both in simulation runs and the real robot operation.

The GUI is brought up as a separate ROS node, hence it is connected with various ROS-based modalities of the complete software architecture. As shown in 7), The teleoperation GUI is a two-page dialog window and can be used to control the robot in either low-level servo control, providing commands directly to the Stewart mechanisms, or in high level control by providing linear and angular velocity commands to the robot drill head. These two modes of control are further explained in the following two sections, respectively.

Fig. 7. Teleoperation GUI. The Stewart control page is shown.

1) *Stewart actuator commands (direct Stewart control)*: Each Stewart module can be controlled individually by adjusting the desired propulsion, pitch and yaw angle of the module via slider interfaces. These three commands are also indicated to the user in the respective text boxes. The combined commands are mapped to specific displacements of the Stewart linear actuators. To achieve that we use a transformation applying the inverse kinematics of the Stewart mechanism. Thus:

- For the propulsion Stewart mechanism, the relation is $l_1^p = l_2^p = l_3^p$, where l_x^r are the propulsion module linear

actuator commands and p is the desired position of the propulsion module, i.e. the user command.

- For the steering Stewart mechanism, the lengths of the steering module linear actuators are given as a function of the the desired pitch and yaw angles (θ and ψ), and calculated based on inverse kinematics of the steering mechanism, as shown in the equations below

$$l_1^r = a_c + \frac{d_c}{2} \sin \theta \cos \psi + \frac{\sqrt{3}d_c}{2} \cos \theta \sin \psi \quad (1)$$

$$l_2^r = a_c + \frac{d_c}{2} \sin \theta \cos \psi - \frac{\sqrt{3}d_c}{2} \cos \theta \sin \psi \quad (2)$$

$$l_3^r = a_c + d_c \sin \theta \cos \psi \quad (3)$$

where l_x^r are the steering module linear actuators commands, θ and ψ are the pitch and yaw use commands, a_c is the center position home position) of the linear actuators and d_c is the distance between the center of the rotating plate and plane of the base onto which the linear actuators are mounted.

The resulting linear actuator commands are also displayed to the user in the respective textboxes. The propulsion plate commands are shown at the left while the rotation plate commands at the right. Since the motion of the linear actuators is governed by PID controllers, the actual positions of the latter are also available to the user (the textboxes showing the actual values are found just below the boxes showing the desired values). Finally, the propulsion, pitch and yaw states that were actually achieved by its module are indicated in the Feedback section. To compute the real states, we apply the forward kinematics:

- For the propulsion the linear actuator length is given by: $\left(\frac{l_1^r + l_2^r + l_3^r}{3}\right)$
- For the pitch and yaw angles the inverse kinematics in vector form can be approximated by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} l_1^r - a_c \\ l_2^r - a_c \\ l_3^r - a_c \end{bmatrix} = \frac{d_c}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \sqrt{3} \\ 1 & -\sqrt{3} \\ -2 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sin \theta \cos \psi \\ \cos \theta \sin \psi \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Using the pseudo-inverse, we get:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sin \theta \cos \psi \\ \cos \theta \sin \psi \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{3d_c} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & -2 \\ \sqrt{3} & -\sqrt{3} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} l_1^r - a_c \\ l_2^r - a_c \\ l_3^r - a_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

For small angles, we can get directly:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ \psi \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{3d_c} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & -2 \\ \sqrt{3} & -\sqrt{3} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} l_1^r - a_c \\ l_2^r - a_c \\ l_3^r - a_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

However, if we need better results we can compute the angles by solving the equations below:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{3d_c} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & -2 \\ \sqrt{3} & -\sqrt{3} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} l_1^r - a_c \\ l_2^r - a_c \\ l_3^r - a_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

$$\theta = 0.5(\sin^{-1}(\alpha + \beta) + \sin^{-1}(\alpha - \beta)) \quad (8)$$

$$\psi = \sin^{-1}(\alpha + \beta) - \theta \quad (9)$$

Due to the limits of the linear actuators, there are also limits to the commanded angles that the user can be set to the pitch and yaw angles of the Stewart rotating plate. As the forward kinematics are not straight forward, we compute the valid space for the badger robot Stewart mechanism (i.e., $d_c = 0.105$ and $a_c = 0.025$), which is depicted in figure 8. For simplicity we can reduce the available space using a symmetric polygon. Thus, the limits for a given pitch angle command (θ) and for a given yaw angle command (ψ) respectively can be written as:

$$|\psi_{max}| = -2\theta + 0.481, \quad \theta \in [0, 0.2405] \quad (10)$$

$$|\theta_{max}| = -0.5\psi + 0.2405, \quad \psi \in [0, 0.2405] \quad (11)$$

Three buttons are provided in order to control the locking of

Fig. 8. Valid steering space of the Stewart mechanism.

each service module, by activating the corresponding clamp. This is a binary operation that is performed manually by the user. At this point, it is important to highlight that improper locking sequence will result to incorrect Gait motion of the robot. Of course, the Drill Lock button is not designated for locking the drill head in the real robot since there is no such a mechanism available. Hence, this button is only used in the simulation framework, while it can be also used to reset the odometry state either in simulation or in the real robot.

2) *Velocity control*: The user interface for the high-level Velocity Control module is depicted in Fig. (9). In this mode of tele-operation, commands are sent in the form of body velocities on the drill head frame. A master START/STOP button controls the initialization and termination of the motion. As it can be observed, the front-end of the Velocity Control Page is significantly lighter and simpler than the Stewart Control Page. More specifically, three main functionalities are considered: a) Linear Speed, b) Pitch Rate and c) Yaw Rate. The drill head linear speed is controlled by a slider, while the pitch and yaw rates are controlled via rotational knobs.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper an advanced and intuitive HRI interface that allows the tele-operation of BADGER's ground and underground robots has been presented. The integrated architecture has been illustrated along with the libraries and mechanisms that have

Fig. 9. Velocity control pane.

been implemented to provide a comprehensive representation of the designated scanning area, and the proper tools that allow the operator to effortlessly control the robots. Using the latest technologies in HRI design techniques and web application development we managed to build an interface that can accurately visualize the remote area along with additional geospatial information and detected underground objects while at the same time providing tools for automatic robot path generation and teleoperation. Thus, the operator is offered an effective and easy to use interface with increased situation awareness and error handling abilities in order to perform underground drilling operations.

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